

1,3-Dipolar cycloadditions of nitrones derived from protocatechuric aldehyde methylene ether : synthesis of isoxazole-4,6-diones

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A series of cycloadducts, identified as *cis*-2,5-diaryl-3-(3',4'-methylenedioxy phenyl)-4*H*,2,3,3*a*,5,6,6*a*-hexahydropyrrolo[3,4-*d*]isoxazole-4,6-dione **3** have been prepared by cycloaddition of nitrone **2** with variously substituted maleimides. All the cycloadducts are characterised by various spectral studies. The nitrones have been prepared from protocatechuric aldehyde methylene ether **1**.

1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition reactions have been the focus of great attention in synthetic organic chemistry for construction of 5-membered heterocyclic rings^{1,2}. Among the different cycloadditions, 1,3-dipolar nitrone cycloaddition is a powerful reaction³, where nitrones on facile cycloaddition with olefins and acetylenes yield respective isoxazolidines and isoxazolines derivatives⁴⁻⁷ with the generation of new stereogenic center/centers in the products⁸⁻¹⁰. Though the cycloaddition of *C,N*-diaryl nitrones with *N*-substituted maleimides and other dipolarophiles is known in literature, its systematic studies are still useful to synthesize novel

heterocycles of varied structures. We report herein a detailed study on the stereochemistry and the reactivity of cycloaddition reaction^{11,12} of nitrones (generated from the reaction of protocatechuric aldehyde methylene ether and various *N*-arylhydroxylamines)^{13,14} with a variety of *N*-aryl maleimides^{15,16}.

Results and discussion

The 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reaction of *C*-(3',4'-methylenedioxy phenyl)-*N*-arylnitrones **2** with *N*-arylmaleimides have been carried out by refluxing equimolar quanti-

Table 1. Analytical data for 2,5-diaryl-3-(3',4'-methylenedioxy phenyl)-4*H*-2,3,3*a*,5,6,6*a*-hexahydropyrrolo[3,4-*d*]isoxazole-4,6-diones **3**

Compd	X	Y	Yield (%)	M p ^a (°C)	Mol formula	Analysis % (Calcd /Found)			
						C	H	N	Cl
3a	H	H	80	212–214	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₅	69.56 (68.10)	4.34 (4.12)	6.76 (5.5)	–
3b	4-CH ₃	H	78	203–205	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₅	70.09 (69.01)	4.67 (4.42)	6.54 (6.20)	–
3c	4-Cl	H	79	211–214	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₅ Cl	64.21 (63.92)	3.79 (3.50)	6.24 (6.02)	7.91 (6.98)
3d	4-NO ₂	H	71	215–218	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₇	62.7 (61.92)	3.70 (3.65)	9.15 (9.01)	–
3e	4-OCH ₃	H	74	216–217	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₆	67.5 (66.80)	4.50 (4.23)	6.30 (6.01)	–
3f	4-OC ₂ H ₅	H	76	198–201	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₆	68.12 (67.65)	4.80 (4.21)	6.1 (5.8)	–
3g	H	CH ₃	78	218–222	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₅	70.09 (69.08)	4.67 (4.51)	6.54 (6.02)	–
3h	4-CH ₃	CH ₃	79	224–226	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₅	70.5 (69.81)	4.91 (4.23)	6.33 (5.96)	–
3i	4-Cl	CH ₃	74	209–211	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₅ Cl	64.86 (63.82)	4.1 (3.9)	6.05 (5.86)	7.67 (6.91)
3j	4-NO ₂	CH ₃	72	220–222	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₇	63.42 (62.8)	4.01 (3.65)	8.87 (8.43)	–
3k	4-OCH ₃	CH ₃	74	215–216	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₆	68.12 (67.61)	4.80 (4.56)	6.1 (5.9)	–
3l	4-OC ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	76	208–211	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₆	68.64 (67.89)	5.08 (4.91)	5.93 (5.51)	–
3m	H	Cl	72	195–199	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₅ Cl	64.2 (63.56)	3.79 (3.41)	6.24 (6.01)	7.91 (6.81)
3n	4-CH ₃	Cl	70	212–215	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₅ Cl	64.86 (63.91)	4.10 (4.01)	6.05 (6.01)	7.67 (6.89)
3o	4-Cl	Cl	75	220–221	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₅ Cl ₂	59.62 (59.41)	3.31 (3.20)	5.79 (4.89)	14.6 (13.9)
3p	4-NO ₂	Cl	74	222–223	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₅ Cl	58.35 (58.01)	3.24 (2.86)	8.51 (7.95)	7.19 (7.0)
3q	4-OCH ₃	Cl	78	209–211	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₆ Cl	64.8 (63.6)	4.10 (4.01)	6.05 (5.91)	7.67 (6.98)
3r	4-OC ₂ H ₅	Cl	76	214–215	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₆ Cl	65.4 (65.01)	4.40 (4.31)	5.87 (5.56)	7.4 (6.89)

^aAll the melting points are uncorrected

ties of both the reagents in sodium dried benzene. The usual work up of the reaction mixture provided crude product **3** as a single stereoisomer in good yield, which has been recrystallised from hexane-ethylacetate (3 : 1) mixture (Scheme 1). The cycloadducts **3** have been identified as *cis*-2,5-diaryl-3-(3',4'-methylenedioxy phenyl)-4*H*-2,3,3*a*,5,6,6*a*-hexahydropyrrolo[3,4-*d*]isoxazole-4,6-diones with respect to proton H₃ on azomethine carbon *cis* to hydrogen H_{3*a*} and H_{6*a*} on the *N*-arylmaleimide moiety.

Table 2. IR spectral data for 2,5-diaryl-3-(3',4'-methylenedioxy phenyl)-4*H*-2,3,3*a*,5,6,6*a*-hexahydropyrrolo[3,4-*d*]isoxazole-4,6-diones **3**

Compd.	>C=O	>N=O	>C-N	Others
3a	1725, 1690	1260, 1203	1380, 1348, 1142, 1098	
3b	1720, 1689	1263, 1205	1370, 1352, 1130, 1100	
3c	1725, 1700	1269, 1204	1382, 1365, 1140, 1110	1075 (C-Cl st.)
3d	1722, 1692	1265, 1200	1370, 1360, 1145, 1115	1530, 1513, 1350 (C-NO ₂ st.)
3e	1728, 1690	1270, 1205	1385, 1365, 1143, 1110	1020 (C-OCH ₃ st.)
3f	1725, 1680	1250, 1190	1387, 1355, 1148, 1110	
3g	1720, 1675	1263, 1204	1394, 1377, 1145, 1120	
3h	1720, 1609	1242, 1203	1360, 1320, 1183, 1094	
3i	1726, 1675	1263, 1200	1390, 1360, 1182, 1095	1080 (C-Cl st.)
3j	1732, 1620	1220, 1155	1380, 1350, 1190, 1135	1525, 1510, 1360 (C-NO ₂ st.)
3k	1725, 1675	1263, 1182	1360, 1325, 1190, 1120	1299, 1030 (C-OCH ₃ st.)
3l	1720, 1680	1220, 1145	1375, 1330, 1195, 1140	
3m	1719, 1680	1256, 1200	1383, 1350, 1145, 1100	1090 (C-Cl st.)
3n	1725, 1675	1263, 1182	1387, 1340, 1170, 1110	1088 (C-Cl st.)
3o	1719, 1695	1152, 1150	1399, 1375, 1180, 1110	1090 (C-Cl st.)
3p	1725, 1690	1248, 1192	1383, 1370, 1180, 1100	1530, 1523, 1340 (C-NO ₂), 1090 (C-Cl st.)
3q	1719, 1680	1256, 1200	1383, 1350, 1145, 1100	1320, 1040, 1019 (C-OCH ₃ st.), 1075 (C-Cl st.)
3r	1719, 1695	1152, 1150	1399, 1375, 1180, 1110	1083 (C-Cl st.)

These products **3** have been characterised through their, IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and mass spectra in addition to their melting points and elemental analysis. The physical and IR data for these products are reported in Tables 1 and 2.

In the infrared spectra these cycloadducts show strong absorption bands in the region 1732–1719 cm⁻¹ which have been assigned to carbonyl groups of maleimide moiety.

X = H, CH₃, Cl, NO₂, OCH₃, OC₂H₅

Reagents and reaction conditions : (i) + NHOR, ethanol, stirring 30 min; (ii) *N*-substituted phenyl maleimide, C₆H₆ reflux 5–8 h.

Scheme 1

The ¹H NMR spectra of **3g** shows a multiplet at δ 6.75–7.47 that has been assigned to 12 aromatic protons. A doublet at δ 5.93 has been assigned to two protons of >CH₂ group with *J* = 3.77 Hz. A doublet at δ 5.26 has been assigned to proton H_{6*a*} showing having coupling constant *J*_{6*a*–3*a*} = 7.92 Hz. A doublet at δ 4.72 has been assigned to proton H₃ having coupling constant *J*_{3–3*a*} = 9.02 Hz, a quartet at δ 4.01 which is assigned to proton H_{3*a*} having coupling constant *J*_{3*a*–6*a*} = 7.67 and *J*_{3*a*–3} = 8.92 Hz respectively. A singlet at δ 2.26 is assigned to CH₃ group. The proton H₃ shows vicinal coupling both with H_{6*a*} and H_{3*a*} as all the cycloadducts show typical coupling constant *J*_{3*a*–6*a*} and *J*_{3*a*–3} ≈ 7.50–9.20 Hz. It indicates that the three protons H₃, H_{3*a*} and H_{6*a*} are in *cis*-orientation with one another.

Similarly ¹³C NMR spectral studies of these cycloadducts show signals at δ 58.12–59.83 assigned to C_{3*a*}, δ 71.94–72.91 assigned to C₃ and δ 80.92–82.26 assigned to C_{6*a*}. There occur two separate signals for two carbonyl functions of maleimide moiety at δ 164.28–165.98 and δ 165.20–166.99.

A high resolution mass spectra of **3g** displays molecular ion peak at *m/z* 428 (86.4). This parent ion undergoes retro-cycloaddition and gives a peak at *m/z* 255 (18.5) attributed to parent nitrone after elimination of *N*-arylmaleimide moiety 174 (4.9) and 173 (34.2). On further fragmentation this gives ions *m/z* 135 (4.1) and 105 (100.0). The peak at 91 (46.5) attributed to anilinium ion, together with other characteristic ions found at *m/z* 77, 121, 238, 135 and 119.

Conclusion :

The structure of **3** was confirmed on the basis of various spectral studies. All the products obtained are *cis*-2,5-

Note

diaryl-3-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)-4*H*,2,3,3*a*,5,6,6*a*-hexahydropyrrolo[3,4-*d*]isoxazole-4,6-dione derivatives.

It seems that during these 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition nitrone in the transition state have the *trans*-orientation where the non-bonded steric interactions are minimum and secondary orbital interactions become dominant. Ortho hydrogens of *C*-aryl ring would be deshielded when they are closer to nitrone oxygen. Therefore, all nitrones have *trans*-orientation around >C=N<. At the transition state the preferred approach of dipole and dipolarophile is one where the bonding interaction between the two substrates and steric interactions are minimum. There is less steric interaction therefore, secondary orbital interactions become dominant and results in *cis*-isomer as major product.

General technique :

IR spectra were recorded with FT IR Perkin-Elmer RX-I instrument using nujol at Punjabi University, Patiala. NMR spectra (¹H and ¹³C) were recorded on 300 MHz Bruker AC-300G instrument with TMS as internal standard and CDCl₃ + DMSO as solvent at SAIF, Punjab University, Chandigarh. Mass spectrum was recorded on VG-70S instrument at SAIF, Punjab University, Chandigarh. All Melting points have been determined by Gallen-Kamp apparatus and are uncorrected.

Experimental

This cycloaddition reaction was carried out following a similar procedure in each case. A typical procedure is given below :

Synthesis of C-(3',4'-methylenedioxy phenyl)-N-aryl nitrones (2a-c) : These nitrones have been synthesised by similar procedure as reported in literature^{9,10}, **2a** : m.p. 135°; **2b** : 142–145°, **2c** : 143–147°.

*Synthesis of 2,5-diaryl-3-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)-4*H*,2,3,3*a*,5,6,6*a*-hexahydropyrrolo[3,4-*d*]isoxazole-4,6-diones (3a-r)* : *General procedure* : To *C*-(3',4'-methylenedioxy phenyl)-*N*-aryl nitrone (0.01 mol) in a 100 ml RB flask were added *N*-arylmaleimide (0.01 mol) and sodium dried benzene (50 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 5–8 h cooled under tap water. The crude product separated was filtered and recrystallised from hexane/ethylacetate (3 : 1) to give the pure product.

3a : 80%, 212–214°, ¹H NMR δ_H 4.0 (1H, q, H_{3a}, *J* 7.49 and 8.94 Hz), 4.72 (1H, d, H₃, *J* 9.057 Hz), 5.2 (1H, d, H_{6a}, *J* 7.88 Hz), 5.9 (2H, m, >CH₂), 6.75–7.51 (13H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR δ_C 58.76 (C_{3a}), 72.22 (C₃), 81.98 (C_{6a}), 101.24 (>CH₂), 105.77–148.44 (aromatic carbons), 164.74 and 165.20 (>C=O); MS : *m/z* (%) 414 (M⁺, 82.5), 225 (100).

3b : 78%, 203–205°, ¹H NMR δ_H 2.31 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.97 (1H, q, H_{3a}, *J* 7.92 and 8.99 Hz), 4.75 (1H, d, H₃, *J* 9.12 Hz), 5.08 (1H, d, H_{6a}, *J* 7.87 Hz), 5.9 (2H, m, >CH₂), 6.56–7.52 (12H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR δ_C 20.78 (CH₃), 59.09 (C_{3a}), 72.46 (C₃), 81.91 (C_{6a}), 101.36 (>CH₂), 106.52–149.51 (aromatic carbons), 165.18 and 166.66 (>C=O); MS : *m/z* (%) 428 (M⁺, 87.4), 430 (M⁺+2, 4.7), 105 (100).

3c : 79%, 211–214°, ¹H NMR δ_H 4.02 (1H, q, H_{3a}, *J* 7.61 and 9.12 Hz), 4.64 (1H, d, H₃, *J* 9.057 Hz), 5.23 (1H, d, H_{6a}, *J* 7.97 Hz), 5.9 (2H, m, >CH₂), 6.81–7.63 (12H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR δ_C 58.91 (C_{3a}), 72.82 (C₃), 82.05 (C_{6a}), 101.05 (>CH₂), 106.52–149.85 (aromatic carbons), 164.28 and 166.52 (>C=O); MS : *m/z* (%) 448.5 (M⁺, 100), 105 (87.6).

3d : 71%, 215–218°, ¹H NMR δ_H 4.16 (1H, q, H_{3a}, *J* 7.82 and 9.01 Hz), 4.71 (1H, d, H₃, *J* 9.057 Hz), 5.01 (1H, d, H_{6a}, *J* 7.88 Hz), 5.94 (2H, m, >CH₂), 6.83–7.67 (12H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR δ_C 59.25 (C_{3a}), 72.41 (C₃), 82.16 (C_{6a}), 101.16 (>CH₂), 106.58–151.29 (aromatic carbons), 165.26 and 166.52 (>C=O); MS : *m/z* (%) 459 (M⁺, 88.4), 225 (100).

3e : 74%, 216–217°, ¹H NMR δ_H 3.72 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.23 (1H, q, H_{3a}, *J* 7.62 and 9.017 Hz), 4.75 (1H, d, H₃, *J* 9.057 Hz), 5.01 (1H, d, H_{6a}, *J* 7.50 Hz), 5.93 (2H, m, >CH₂), 6.51–7.62 (12H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR δ_C 55.34 (OCH₃), 58.26 (C_{3a}), 72.49 (C₃), 81.78 (C_{6a}), 101.22 (>CH₂), 106.71–148.75 (aromatic carbons), 165.11 and 165.98 (C=O); MS : *m/z* (%) 444 (M⁺, 86.8), 105 (100).

3f : 76%, 198–201°, ¹H NMR δ_H 1.46 (3H, t, OCH₂CH₃), 3.91 (2H, q, OCH₂CH₃), 4.01 (1H, q, H_{3a}, *J* 7.94 and 8.97 Hz), 4.73 (1H, d, H₃, *J* 9.057 Hz), 5.15 (1H, d, H_{6a}, *J* 7.88 Hz), 5.92 (2H, m, >CH₂), 6.58–7.62 (12H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR δ_C 24.56 (OCH₂CH₃), 53.12 (OCH₂CH₃), 58.12 (C_{3a}), 71.94 (C₃), 71.94 (C₃), 80.92 (C_{6a}), 101.14 (CH₂), 106.71–149.15 (aromatic carbons), 165.21 and 166.11 (>C=O); MS : *m/z* (%) 458 (M⁺, 89.4), 187 (100).

3g : 78%, 218–222°, ¹H NMR δ_H 2.23 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.16 (1H, q, H_{3a}, *J* 7.51 and 8.97 Hz), 4.73 (1H, d, H₃, *J* 9.057 Hz), 5.13 (1H, d, H_{6a}, *J* 7.47 Hz), 5.94 (2H, m, >CH₂), 6.55–7.59 (12H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR δ_C 20.91 (CH₃), 59.21 (C_{3a}), 72.15 (C₃), 80.92 (C_{6a}), 101.12 (CH₂), 105.91–148.62 (aromatic carbons), 165.12 and 166.65 (C=O); MS : *m/z* (%) 428 (M⁺, 87.8), 416 (M⁺+2, 5.2), 173 (100).

3h : 79%, 224–226°, ¹H NMR δ_H 2.25 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.31 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.17 (1H, q, H_{3a}, *J* 7.926 and 8.94 Hz), 4.74 (1H, d, H₃, *J* 9.057 Hz), 5.06 (1H, d, H_{6a}, *J* 7.87 Hz), 5.94 (2H, m, >CH₂), 6.52–7.78 (12H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR

δ_C 20.29 (CH₃), 20.36 (CH₃), 58.71 (C_{3a}), 72.08 (C₃), 81.85 (C_{6a}), 101.42 (>CH₂), 106.48–150.22 (aromatic carbons), 165.19 and 166.56 (>C=O); MS : *m/z* (%) 442 (M⁺, 89.3), 430 (M⁺+2, 4.5), 105 (100).

3i : 74%, 209–211°, ¹H NMR δ_H 2.39 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.95 (1H, q, H_{3a}, *J* 7.94 and 9.11 Hz), 4.67 (1H, d, H₃, *J* 9.17 Hz), 5.23 (1H, d, H_{6a}, *J* 7.97 Hz), 5.91 (2H, m, >CH₂), 6.54–7.59 (12H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR δ_C 20.31 (CH₃), 59.83 (C_{3a}), 72.59 (C₃), 82.21 (C_{6a}), 101.65 (>CH₂), 106.71–150.91 (aromatic carbons), 165.26 and 166.52 (>C=O); MS : *m/z* (%) 462.55 (M⁺, 100).

3j : 72%, 220–222°, ¹H NMR δ_H 2.25 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.21 (1H, q, H_{3a}, *J* 7.65 and 8.97 Hz), 4.46 (1H, d, H₃, *J* 9.08 Hz), 5.1 (1H, d, H_{6a}, *J* 7.42 Hz), 5.93 (2H, m, >CH₂), 6.56–7.78 (12H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR δ_C 20.28 (CH₃), 59.78 (C_{3a}), 72.56 (C₃), 82.26 (C_{6a}), 101.26 (>CH₂), 106.65–151.78 (aromatic carbons), 165.28 and 166.65 (>C=O); MS : *m/z* (%) 473 (M⁺, 79.8), 270 (100).

3k : 74%, 215–216°, ¹H NMR δ_H 2.19 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.91 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.02 (1H, q, H_{3a}, *J* 7.97 and 9.09 Hz), 4.73 (1H, d, H₃, *J* 9.12 Hz), 5.12 (1H, d, H_{6a}, *J* 7.88 Hz), 5.87 (2H, m, >CH₂), 6.52–7.75 (12H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR δ_C 20.76 (CH₃), 54.89 (OCH₃), 59.01 (C_{3a}), 72.16 (C₃), 82.12 (C_{6a}), 101.76 (>CH₂), 106.78–149.69 (aromatic carbons), 165.62 and 166.23 (>C=O); MS : *m/z* (%) 458 (M⁺, 100).

3l : 76%, 208–211°, ¹H NMR δ_H 1.31 (3H, t, OCH₂CH₃), 2.24 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.20 (2H, q, OCH₂CH₃), 4.25 (1H, q, H_{3a}, *J* 7.82 and 9.01 Hz), 4.76 (1H, d, H₃, *J* 9.057 Hz), 5.14 (1H, d, H_{6a}, *J* 7.88 Hz), 5.96 (2H, m, >CH₂), 6.67–7.89 (12H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR δ_C 20.78 (CH₃), 24.91 (OCH₂CH₃), 53.26 (OCH₂CH₃), 58.29 (C_{3a}), 72.01 (C₃), 81.29 (C_{6a}), 101.17 (>CH₂), 106.74–149.47 (aromatic carbons), 165.46 and 166.99 (>C=O); MS : *m/z* (%) 472 (M⁺, 87.9), 430 (M⁺+2, 4.2), 187 (100).

3m : 72%, 195–199°, ¹H, NMR δ_H 3.97 (1H, q, H_{3a}, *J* 7.84 and 9.091 Hz), 4.45 (1H, d, H₃, *J* 9.057 Hz), 5.14 (1H, d, H_{6a}, *J* 7.99 Hz), 5.92 (2H, m, >CH₂), 6.8–7.85 (12H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR δ_C 58.91 (C_{3a}), 76.62 (C₃), 82.12 (C_{6a}), 101.74 (>CH₂), 106.72–151.48 (aromatic carbons), 166.71 and 166.97 (C=O); MS : *m/z* (%) 449.5 (M⁺, 78.78), 105 (100).

3n : 70%, 212–215°, ¹H NMR δ_H 2.23 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.01 (1H, q, H_{3a}, *J* 7.97 and 9.097 Hz), 4.47 (1H, d, H₃, *J* 9.02 Hz), 5.11 (1H, d, H_{6a}, *J* 7.81 Hz), 5.89 (2H, m, >CH₂), 6.56–7.65 (12H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR δ_C 21.20 (CH₃), 58.72 (C_{3a}), 72.51 (C₃), 82.10 (C_{6a}), 101.97 (>CH₂), 106.78–151.67 (aromatic carbons), 165.98 and 166.19 (>C=O); MS : *m/z* (%) 463.5 (M⁺, 77.4), 465.5 (M⁺+2, 4.2), 105 (100).

3o : 75%, 220–221°, ¹H NMR δ_H 4.21 (1H, q, H_{3a}, *J* 7.77 and 8.97 Hz), 4.81 (1H, d, H₃, *J* 8.99 Hz), 5.15 (1H, d, H_{6a}, *J* 7.97 Hz), 5.93 (2H, m, >CH₂), 6.85–7.65 (12H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR δ_C 58.91 (C_{3a}), 72.75 (C₃), 81.97 (C_{6a}), 101.76 (>CH₂), 106.78–152.09 (aromatic carbons), 165.12 and 166.56 (>C=O); MS : *m/z* (%) 484 (M⁺, 100).

3p : 74%, 222–223°, ¹H NMR δ_H 4.16 (1H, q, H_{3a}, *J* 7.93 and 9.18 Hz), 4.73 (1H, d, H₃, *J* 9.057 Hz), 5.21 (1H, d, H_{6a}, *J* 7.99 Hz), 5.92 (2H, m, >CH₂), 6.82–7.51 (12H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR δ_C 58.72 (C_{3a}), 72.91 (C₃), 81.76 (C_{6a}), 101.62 (CH₂), 106.12–152.20 (aromatic carbons), 165.15 and 166.45 (>C=O); MS : *m/z* (%) 494.5 (M⁺, 89.4), 495 (M⁺+1, 2.7), 77 (100).

3q : 78%, 209–211°, ¹H NMR δ_H 3.83 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.32 (1H, q, H_{3a}, *J* 7.82 and 8.97 Hz), 4.45 (1H, d, H₃, *J* 9.057 Hz), 4.69 (1H, d, H_{6a}, *J* 7.56 Hz), 5.91 (2H, m, >CH₂), 6.74–7.56 (12H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR δ_C 54.47 (OCH₃), 59.12 (C_{3a}), 72.17 (C₃), 82.01 (C_{6a}), 101.26 (>CH₂), 106.17–150.12 (aromatic carbons), 165.91 and 166.22 (C=O); MS : *m/z* (%) 479 (M⁺, 100).

3r : 76%, 214–215°, ¹H NMR δ_H 1.62 (3H, t, OCH₂CH₃), 3.82 (2H, q, OCH₂CH₃), 4.21 (1H, q, H_{3a}, *J* 8.01 and 9.03 Hz), 4.7 (1H, d, H₃, *J* 8.99 Hz), 5.21 (1H, d, H_{6a}, *J* 8.45 Hz), 5.94 (2H, m, >CH₂), 6.67–7.69 (12H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR δ_C 24.12 (OCH₂CH₃), 52.91 (OCH₂CH₃), 58.27 (C_{3a}), 72.17 (C₃), 82.02 (C_{6a}), 101.72 (>CH₂), 106.26–149.71 (aromatic carbons), 165.26 and 165.97 (C=O); MS : *m/z* (%) 482.5 (M⁺, 81.3), 259.5 (100).

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